

WEAR BEHAVIOR OF SOME CUTTING TOOLS IN TURNING OF SILVER-IMPREGNATED GRAPHITE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In order to solve the problems of heavy tool wear and poor surface quality in turning of silver-impregnated graphite composites (SIGC), systematically turning experiments of tools with different materials and cutting conditions were performed in this paper. Comparative chip formation mechanisms induced between turning conventional graphite and silver-impregnated graphite composites were revealed. The experimental results indicate that the polycrystalline diamond (PCD) cutter has a distinguished advantage of durability over both coated and uncoated carbide tools when cutting SIGC. In addition, the tool wear, the feed rate and the cutting depth are the predominant factors of the surface quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mechanical seal has been widely used throughout industry to minimize or eliminate leakage in oil pumps, mixers, and other rotating equipment due to its excellent mechanical properties such as reliable operation, long service life and low power consumption [1]. When it comes to new applications in severe working conditions of high temperature and pressure, higher requirements on material performance are put forward [2]. Silver-impregnated graphite composites (SIGC) with a continuous three-dimensional reticulate silver and porous graphite have some specific demands as a new type of sealing material. The addition of silver impregnant in SIGC allows reducing the open porosity, micro-crack, and other defects, which avoids the crack propagation and improving the gas tightness compared with conventional graphite as result [3].

In practical application on manufacturing mechanical seals, graphite materials usually require a subsequent cutting/grinding to meet the size and assembly requirements [4]. Owing to the pressure on the graphite from pre-stressed silver skeleton, the strength of SIGC is more than twice as high as that of its graphite matrix. Unique structure and properties of SIGC inevitably induce some difficulties in its machining, such as poor machining quality and heavy tool wear [2]. It is necessary to understand the physical mechanism of the material removal of the machining process. Compared to the machining aspects of conventional graphite, there are few investigations on SIGC and the mechanism are less understood. It has been reported that poor processing quality and high reject rate of machined SIGC parts have limit the use of this material.

Conventional graphite is characterized of high porosity, low flexural and compressive strength. In the machining process, graphite materials break along the large amounts of micro-pores and chips fall off in a massive manner [5]. The cutters are subject to load shock, requiring higher toughness of tool material to ensure acceptable tool life [6]. In addition, pits appear on the machined surface, resulting in uneven cutting thickness in the next cutting, further increasing the load attack on the cutter. However, due to the high density of SIGC and the supporting role of silver on the graphite matrix, the chips are generated in the forms of powdery hard particles around cutting edge under the circumstance of machining SIGC. Cutting tools encounter lower load attack, but larger cutting force compared with cutting conventional graphite.

Based on the analysis of the constituents and structures of SIGC, contrast tests were conducted on turning SIGC with cutters of different materials and cutting parameters in this paper. The material removal mechanism in the cutting process was also investigated. The cutting force, tool wear and machined surface quality of different tool materials and processing parameters were discussed in detail, and the optimum process of turning SIGC with high efficiency and high quality was suggested in this paper.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials: workpiece and tool

The materials used in the tests are SIGC rods. The mechanical and physical properties are shown in Table 1. Due to the impregnation of silver as reinforcing phase into the graphite matrix at high temperature and pressure, the open porosity of SIGC is less than 2.5%, and the compressive and flexural strength of the material is more than one times higher than that of the graphite matrix. The cylindrical rods used in the experiment are of size $\Phi 50 \text{ mm} \times 80 \text{ mm}$. A square sample of size $10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm}$ was processed and ground for energy disperse spectroscopy (EDS) and X ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. Fig. 1 shows the surface micrograph and the results of EDS composition analysis on points A and B respectively by scanning electron microscopy (Hitachi S3400). Ductile silver is filled in almost all pores inner graphite matrix. Pores are rarely observed on the surface, and the material is closely continuous. By EDS composition analysis, it is found that the element in the dark region (point A) is carbon and the element in the light region (point B) is only silver.

Category	Value
Shore hardness	70
Flexural strength / MPa	≥ 70
Compressive strength / MPa	≥ 200
Open porosity / %	≤ 2.5
Volume density / g cm^{-3}	2.9
Operating temperature / $^{\circ}\text{C}$	1350

Table1 Properties of SIGC [7].

Figure 1: SEM micrograph and EDS analysis of SIGC.

XRD composition analysis (D/Max 2500VL/PC) was used to detect the components of SIGC (Fig. 2). It can be found that a low diffraction peak shaped like a steamed bun occurs where 2θ value is between $20 \sim 30^\circ$, which correspond to elemental carbon (Graphite-3R) only. This is explained as the graphite matrix in SIGC is of no significant directionality and the mechanical properties of the material are isotropic at macroscopic level. 2θ values of 38.0° , 44.2° , 64.3° and 77.34° respectively correspond to the diffraction peak of Ag (111), Ag (200), Ag (220), Ag (311) crystal plane. This means that the material contains only two components, namely graphite and silver (silver-3c). Graphite and silver in SIGC are only mechanically connected without any other joint forms.

Figure 2: Results of XRD composition analysis.

To carry out contrast tests, turning tools of 3 different materials have been used, including uncoated carbide, TiAlN-coating and PCD, and the tool specifications are given in Table 2.

Substrate	Coating	Corner radius (mm)	Rake angle (deg)	Main clearance angle (deg)
cemented carbide	-	0.3969	15	7
cermet	TiAlN	0.3969	15	7
PCD	-	0.2	0	7

Table 2: Tool specifications.

2.2 Experimental procedure

In order to study the effects of tool wear and cutting parameters on cutting force and machined surface quality, a series of experiments on turning SIGC are conducted on the universal lathe (C6140). A simple modification was applied to the tool holder of the lathe for measuring on-line load. Machining test platform and schematic cutting diagram are shown in Fig. 3.

The procedure on cutting of the outer circumference of a round SIGC rod consists of 3 tests with varied tools listed in Table 2. The parameters were as follows: spindle speed (n), 225r/min; the feed rate (f), 0.09 mm/r; cutting depth (a_p), 0.5 mm; and cutting time (t), 7.5min. In addition, a group of L9 (3^4) orthogonal tests using PCD cutter with various parameters (Table 3) were conducted. All turning experiments was performed in dry condition due to the material property.

The morphology of cutter blade and the rounded edge radius were acquired by the 3D contour scanner (Sensofar S neox). Triaxial piezoelectric dynamometer (Kister 9272A, Swiss), charge amplifier (Kister 5070A) and corresponding data acquisition software were used to measure the cutting force. The machined surface morphologies of cutters and SIGC were visualized by scanning

electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S3400) and three-dimensional video microscopy (KH-7700). The surface roughness was measured by portable roughness instrument (Mahr Perthometer M1).

Figure 3: Machining test platform and schematic cutting diagram

Test no.	Spindle speed (rpm)	Feed rate (mm/r)	Cutting depth (mm)
1	104	0.045	0.05
2	104	0.09	0.1
3	104	0.13	0.15
4	225	0.045	0.1
5	225	0.09	0.15
6	225	0.13	0.05
7	315	0.045	0.15
8	315	0.09	0.05
9	315	0.13	0.1

Table 3: Arrangement of the orthogonal experiment L9 (3⁴)

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Chip formation mechanism of SIGC

Fig. 4 shows the surface topography of conventional graphite [8]. It can be observed that some big pores distribute in the conventional graphite while SIGC have no visible pore distribution (Fig. 1). The more and bigger pores, the more interfacial defects the materials have.

The removal process of SIGC is apparently different from that of conventional graphite. The cutting models for explaining the differences of chip formation mechanism between conventional graphite and SIGC have been depicted in Fig. 5.

Figure 4: Profile topography of the conventional graphite [8].

Figure 5: Cutting model of (a) conventional graphite and (b) SIGC

Fig. 5 (a) shows the cutting model of conventional graphite. Due to the existence of microscopic defects such as pores, cracks and other microstructural defects of particle boundaries inside conventional graphite. The cracks generated by extrusion propagate in front of the tool tip and extend downward the free surface, forming massive chips [5]. In addition, pits appear on the machined surface, resulting in uneven cutting thickness in the next cutting, further increasing the load attack on the cutter. The spalling of massive chips also leads to the tool being subject to high frequent load fluctuation, resulting in rapid wear of cutters with fragile material. The cutting model corresponds to the analysis by Schroeter et al [6].

Figure 6: Typical cutting force of (a) conventional graphite [2] and (b) SIGC.

To SIGC, the highly ductile silver is pressed into the porous graphite matrix under high temperature and pressure in the process of material preparation, the micro holes existing in the graphite matrix are filled up. Silver has the effect on supporting graphite matrix and the flexural and compressive strength of SIGC are more than 1 times higher than conventional graphite as result. As shown in Fig. 5 (b), the cutting process of the material changes from intermittent cutting to continuous cutting. The crack of the material generated at the tip of the tool will not extend downward due to the supporting function of the silver skeleton. There will be no pits occurring on the machined surface and

a smooth surface can be obtained eventually. As the strength of the material increases, the pressure on the contact surface between the cutter and the material increases, and a large number of graphite particles generated in the processing scratch the surface of the cutter, resulting in heavier abrasive wear.

The original load signals of turning both conventional graphite and SIGC certify the model (Fig. 6). The thrust force exhibits a huge fluctuation ranging from 0 to 20N for cutting conventional graphite. When it comes to turning SIGC, the force presents relatively stable ranging from 14N to 20N compared to conventional graphite.

3.2 Effect of tool materials on processing SIGC

In order to highlight the material that are more resistant to wear, endurance tests have been performed for uncoated carbide, TiAlN-coated and PCD tools respectively. Fig. 7 represents the dependence of the axial or thrust load F_a , normal load F_n , and tangential load F_t with tool wear under the condition: $n=225\text{rpm}$, $f=0.045\text{mm/r}$, $a_p=0.5\text{mm}$. It can be clearly seen in Fig. 7 that the cutting forces of uncoated and TiAlN-coated carbide cutting tool both increase fast. The influence of the tool wear is more obvious for carbide and TiAlN-coated tools than that for PCD tools. The load evolution of PCD tool is negligible compared to the other two tools. The PCD behaves best when compared to the other two tools. Among all three types of tools, the force increments occur mainly in axial direction, while the cutting forces in normal and tangential direction present minor increment.

Figure 7: Cutting forces with turning time of (a) Uncoated carbide cutter, (b) TiAlN-coated cutter and (c) PCD cutter.

Figure 8: Initial rounded cutting edge of three types of turning tools.

Fig. 8 shows the initial rounded cutting edge of three types of turning tools. The colors in the picture represents the height of the points acquired from the tool surfaces. The initial roundness of cutting edge of PCD cutter is lower than the other two tools, which is 10-20 μm lower than 50-60 μm , 70-80 μm apparently, which explains why the cutting force of PCD cutter is the smallest. The smaller the rounded cutting edge radius, the sharper the cutter, and the easier the material can be removed as result.

Fig. 9 (a) exemplifies a confocal scanning image of a cutting edge at the uncoated carbide tool. A cross-section A-B-C of this image, as displayed in Fig. 9 (b), shows the cutting edge profile. Point A is

a visible inflection point in the cutting edge profile, representing the end point of wear on flank face. The cutting edge radius was obtained by curve fitting to a circular arc around point B with least square. Same observations were conducted on the other two tools, as shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. The cutting edge roundness of PCD cutter after endurance tests is much lower than the uncoated carbide tools and TiAlN-coated cutter, which is nearly $15\mu\text{m}$ lower than $64\mu\text{m}$, $147\mu\text{m}$ respectively. Obvious material loss of uncoated carbide tool results in lower effective clearance angle and larger cutting edge radius. The heavy wear damages the cutting ability and leads to higher compressive stress on cutting SIGC. When it comes to TiAlN-coated tool, there is no obvious material loss on tool surface and the tool shape is of high integrity, ensuring it of better cutting ability. Compared with these two tools, PCD tool shows smallest rounded cutting edge radius and best wear resistance.

Figure 9: Cutting edge geometry measurement of uncoated carbide tool after endurance tests: (a) 3D morphology from confocal scanning and (b) cutting edge profile from a cross section view with cutting edge radius.

Figure 10: Cutting edge geometry measurement of TiAlN-coated carbide tool after endurance tests. (a) 3D morphology from confocal scanning and (b) cutting edge profile from a cross section view with cutting edge radius.

Figure 11: Cutting edge geometry measurement of PCD tool after endurance tests. (a) 3D morphology from confocal scanning and (b) cutting edge profile from a cross section view with cutting edge radius.

Fig. 12 depicts the wear topography of three kinds of turning tools. The various states of the

surface wear appear due to the alternating stress generated by graphite matrix and silver materials on rake and flank face of different cutters. The tool wear to different degree changes the shape of cutting edge. The worn bands appear on both the rake and flank faces of uncoated cemented carbide cutter. The radius of the blade became larger, and the cutting ability decreased obviously as result. The cutting force continued to increase rapidly in the whole experimental process.

Compared to the uncoated carbide cutter and TiAlN coated cutter, PCD tool has the highest hardness and good abrasion resistance among all three kinds of tools, with only slight scratch and abrasion on the cutter surface after endurance tests. The radius of cutting edge are almost unchanged and the cutting force during the whole process is very stable as well.

Figure 12: Wear topography on rake and flank face of three types of turning tools.

3.3 Effect of machining parameters on processing SIGC

Fig. 13 shows the surface micro topographies of the surface of SIGC machined by PCD cutter under different parameters. Holes or cracks were not observed on all surfaces. Due to the randomness of the pore distribution of graphite matrix, there is no obvious regularity in the distribution of graphite and silver on the processed surface. As a whole, silver distributes more on the machined surface of SIGC under the machining parameters of small cutting depth.

Fig. 14 shows the force curves in all three directions of the PCD cutting tool on processing SIGC. Cutting forces increase with the feed speed and cutting depth while spindle speed behaves little effect on them. The cutting forces increase with the increase of feed rate and cutting depth, and decrease with the increase of spindle speed, which are straight related to the material removal rate. Surface roughness is mainly affected by feed rate. The smaller the feeding rate is, the smaller the fracture pits on the machined surface of SIGC occur. Under the cutting conditions of low feed rate, thin uncut silver in SIGC bear heavier extrusion of the flank face, and was deposited on the machined surface. When the feed rate is chosen as a comparatively higher value, the uncut chip thickness reaches the critical value of silver cutting and the silver was sheared off; more graphite were deposited on the machined surface, just as the SEM micro topographies of machined SIGC showed in Fig. 13.

The roughness values of machined SIGC are no higher than $2.05\mu\text{m}$ under every parameter. High quality of machined surface was obtained by PCD cutters. The variation trends of roughness are shown in Fig. 15. The feed rate has a profound effect on the cutting forces. The cutting forces increase with the increase of feed rate, while the influences of cutting depth and spindle speed are negligible when turning SIGC. When feed rate value is fixed as 0.045mm/r , the roughness values can be lower than $Ra1.6\mu\text{m}$ under various spindle speed and cutting depth among all turning tests.

Figure 13: SEM micro topography of machined SIGC.

Figure 14: Cutting force of PCD cutter in orthogonal tests.

Figure 15: Average roughness of PCD cutter in orthogonal tests

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, the influences of tool materials and cutting conditions on turning SIGC were analyzed.

The following conclusions are drawn:

- (1) The material removal process of SIGC is significantly different compared with conventional graphite, requiring cutter of higher hardness to obtain better the material durability.
- (2) TiAlN coating is not suitable for processing SIGC for reducing the cutter's sharpness, falling off quickly during cutting process. PCD tool behaves best cutting performance of more stable and smaller cutting force than carbide and TiAlN-coated tool and extraordinary tool durability.
- (3) Within a certain range of machining parameters, PCD tool has a good surface quality without visible micro-pit defects, and their surface roughness can be lower than $3.2\mu\text{m}$. The cutting force decreases with the rotation speed and increases with feed rate and cutting depth. Low feed rate (0.045mm/r) is beneficial to obtain high machining quality and the value of surface roughness is lower than $1.6\mu\text{m}$.

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